

Social Mobilization in the Czech Republic in Response to the War in Ukraine

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Abstract

This paper analyses the mobilization of Czech civil society in response to the Russian invasion of Ukraine, focusing on how selected non-governmental organizations framed the conflict in their public communications. Drawing on framing theory and employing a qualitative content analysis of websites and Facebook posts, we explore the diagnostic, prognostic, and motivational frames used by six Czech NGOs across the first two years of the war. Our findings reveal a marked divergence between humanitarian organizations, which emphasized individual suffering and aid delivery without politicization, and initiatives aimed at purchasing military equipment, which engaged in explicitly political and moral framing. While the former largely avoided attributing blame or invoking democratic values, the latter employed war rhetoric and mobilized public support through appeals to collective security. The study also captures the temporal shift in public engagement and fundraising efforts, noting a decline in solidarity in the second year of the conflict. We argue that the framing strategies adopted by civil society actors were shaped both by their organizational identities and by the evolving political opportunity structures in the Czech Republic.

Keywords

Ukraine; Czech Republic; social mobilization; hybrid warfare; framing theory

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Introduction

The war in Ukraine triggered enormous social mobilization in the Czech Republic on the pro-Ukraine side, probably due to the parallel personal experience many people had of the Warsaw Pact invasion of Czechoslovakia in 1968, led by the Soviet Union army. This collective memory was conveniently sloganized as “the Russians invade again”. Czech civil society mobilized very quickly and the website We Stand with Ukraine (*Stojíme za Ukrajinou* – www.stojimezaukrajinou.cz) was quickly launched during the first days of the war thanks to a collaboration of volunteers, associations and other organizations with the primary aim of providing essential information to people fleeing the war. The website became the main source of information not only for refugees but also for people willing to support Ukraine.

Researchers have examined the Russian invasion (Stojar, 2023), the impacts of the Russian invasion on the rise of far-right organizations in the Czech Republic (Havlík and Kluknavská, 2023), disinformation connected with the Russian invasion (Šefčíková, 2023) and the way Ukrainians have integrated into Czech society and become one of the most significant national minorities (Leontiyeva, 2016; Melehanych, 2021). However, to our knowledge, no research has been published on the pro-Ukrainian social mobilization in the Czech Republic.

In this paper we focus on the pro-Ukraine mobilization by civil society initiatives during the first two years after the Russian invasion. Employing a case study approach, we analyze organizations' websites and the social media platform Facebook (as one of the most prominent platforms for the mobilization of society) to find out how these media were used in the pro-Ukraine mobilization. We set the following research questions: How is pro-Ukrainian mobilization framed in the Czech Republic? What themes and patterns appear? What are the framing strategies? How they have been evolving over time? At the time of writing this article, the war has been going on for more than two years, so evidence of apathy and habituation to the situation was inevitable. We began the research with curiosity to see how the themes had changed over time to maintain the attention of website visitors. How had the messages been transformed to keep Czechs actively interested and in solidarity?

The article starts with a theoretical and methodological section, followed by an analysis of the political opportunity structures of pro-Ukraine social mobilization in the Czech Republic. The main part of the paper comprises an analysis of the pro-Ukrainian mobilization of organizations working on humanitarian aid in Ukraine, those providing aid for refugees in the Czech Republic and those collecting money to buy weapons and other military equipment. Framing theory was chosen as the basic theoretical guideline as it provides a crucial methodology in social mobilization theories and presents a perfect fit for an explanation of the chosen case studies. It helps us explain the success (or failure) of pro-Ukraine mobilization in the Czech Republic.

Theoretical and methodological considerations

Social mobilization is a complex process that involves the organization and coordination of collective action toward a particular goal or cause; one of the key theoretical methodologies that have been used to understand it is framing theory. This suggests that social movements are successful when they are able effectively to frame their cause in a way that resonates with potential supporters and helps to mobilize collective action (Benford and Snow, 2000). Framing helps to construct the definitions of social and political reality; helps make sense of such a reality; and enables individuals “to locate, perceive, identify and label occurrences within their life space and the world at large” (Snow et al., 1986: 464; Caiani, 2023). This can involve presenting the issue in a way that aligns with pre-existing cultural values and beliefs or reframing the issue in a way that challenges dominant cultural narratives.

In many ways, social mobilization depends on the ability to articulate and communicate thoughts and the ability to construct frames to engage an audience.

Framing theory works with three basic frames: diagnostic framing, prognostic framing and motivational framing (Benford and Snow, 2000). Diagnostic framing involves identifying and defining the problem or issue that the social movement is addressing, including attributing the blame or cause. Prognostic framing involves proposing solutions or courses of action to address the problem or issue. Motivational framing involves appealing to individuals' emotions and values to motivate them to act. It entails the construction of vocabularies of motive providing prompts to action. This framing accents the severity of the problem, the urgency of taking action now rather than later, the moral priority and also the enhancement or elevation of one's status. The appeal to emotions is the central feature of this framing (Snow and Benford, 1988; Benford and Snow, 2000; Snow et al., 2013). Caiani (2023) brings up the issue of temporality, which is important for social mobilization. The frames develop over time; they have dynamic characters.

The research design for this study was qualitative, using a case study approach and the qualitative content analysis method. The text focuses on pro-Ukraine social mobilization in the Czech Republic by Czech citizens, though it might encompass initiatives in cooperation with the Ukrainian diaspora or projects conducted in cooperation between the Czech and Ukraine state administrations (www.zbraneproukrajinu.cz). Initiatives that stem solely from Ukraine, from international organizations or from Czech state agencies, towns or firms are omitted. Czech organizations that are part of an international network, though acting independently, are included. The organization had to be active at the time of collecting the data (August 2024). The website We Stand with Ukraine was chosen as the starting point since it was expected to encompass all the main pro-Ukraine initiatives.

The candidate organizations were divided into three groups: those mainly sending help to Ukraine, those primarily helping refugees in the Czech Republic and those collecting money for weapons. We selected for analysis the two organizations in each category that had gathered the most money by August 2024. Organizations that did not have a special bank account for aid to Ukraine were excluded even if they had a special payment identification number for Ukraine. To be included, an organization had to have its own website and Facebook profile. These organizations were analyzed: People in Need Foundation, Czech Red Cross, Caritas, SIMI, Weapons for Ukraine (henceforth referred to as WfU) and Memory of Nations (henceforth referred to as MoN).

Our data analysis was guided by framing theory; we analyzed the data for diagnostic, prognostic and motivational framing. We searched for key themes and patterns in the data to identify how pro-Ukrainian mobilization was framed in the Czech Republic on the organizations' websites and on Facebook over the first two years of the conflict (24 February 2022 to 24 February 2024). Facebook-post scraper Apify was used to extract the data. We coded Facebook posts that referred to any aspect of the conflict in Ukraine; coded data were organized into categories based on the identified themes. The whole coding and sorting process was inductive with the initial coding schema. Additional codes, which were not captured at the beginning, were added using open coding to ensure we captured all themes and patterns. All the initial codes we have developed for our analyses are listed in Table 1 by type of framing. It should be noted that framing also includes the construction of a collective identity asserting on whose behalf the organization is acting, thus emphasizing awareness of similarity and shared fate (van Stekelenburg and Klandermans, 2013). An organization's collective identity thus entails developing a sense of 'we-ness' that motivates individuals to become activists.

Table 1. Types of framing and initial codes

Type of framing	Description	Initial codes
Diagnostic framing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Identifies the problem or issue that pro-Ukrainian mobilization is addressing – Attributes the blame or causality – Watches how Russian aggression and injustice towards Ukraine is framed – Specific framing – Symbols – Likening – Emotion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Violation of human rights in Ukraine – Violation of democratic values – Killing of civilians – Killing of children – Genocide – The war in Eastern Ukraine – Torture – The need for international support
Prognostic framing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Outlines the possible strategies which would resolve the diagnosed issues – Suggests solutions – Identifies tactics and targets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Public awareness and education campaigns – Fundraising and donation drives – Calls for protests and demonstrations – Coordination of international support for Ukraine – Coordination of national support for Ukraine
Motivational framing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Provides reasons for supporting pro-Ukrainian mobilization – Symbols – Cultural narratives – Emotion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Support for Ukrainian democracy and sovereignty – Solidarity with Ukrainian people – A moral imperative to support human rights and democracy – The importance of defending international law and norms – We-ness (collective identity) – The strategic importance of supporting a democratic and stable Ukraine – The danger of the continuous spread of Russian influence in Eastern Europe – A threat of destabilization of the region – A threat to European security – A setback for democracy and human rights – A negative impact on economic and trade relations

Pro-Ukraine mobilization and political opportunity structures

Kitschelt argues (1986, 58) that a particular set of variables is most useful in explaining the success or failure of social movements. Political opportunity structures are composed of specific configurations of resources, institutional arrangements and historical precedents for social mobilization facilitating or

constraining the development of social movements. Political opportunity structures, therefore, influence the choice of strategies and the impact of social movements on their environments. The Russian invasion of Ukraine resulted in the mobilization of civil society across Europe including the Czech Republic. Grass-roots movements mobilized on both sides, pro-Russia as well as pro-Ukraine.

At the beginning of the Russian invasion of Ukraine the government of the Czech Republic made it clear that the state would stand behind Ukraine and support its fight against Russia. The Czech prime minister, Petr Fiala, visited President Volodymyr Zelensky in Kyiv together with his counterparts from Poland and Slovenia, Mateusz Morawiecki and Janez Janša on 15 March 2022. The aim of this first visit of such high-ranking politicians to Ukraine since the invasion was to support the sovereignty and independence of Ukraine throughout the European Union. The Czech president, Miloš Zeman, previously a promoter of Russian interests in the country, supported the aid to Ukraine and admitted that his earlier relationship with the Russian president, Vladimir Putin, had been a mistake (Pancíř, 2022). The Czech political elites gave a clear signal to the public: the Czech Republic stands beside Ukraine. The Czech mainstream media allied with politicians and, in their broadcasts, firmly endorsed the support for Ukraine, portraying Russia as an aggressor and evoking memories of 1968.

When the EU banned Russian media outlets RT and Sputnik from broadcasting, in spring 2022 the Czech government also temporarily blocked a number of disinformation websites that amplified Russian propaganda⁴. This was met with resistance and appeals for freedom of opinion; the disinformation websites were unblocked in June 2022. The behavior of political elites who supported Ukraine in word and deed significantly shaped public opinion, which became very supportive of the Ukrainian case. According to a public opinion poll in April 2022, 81% of respondents disapproved of the Russian invasion and more than two-thirds (74%) perceived Russia as the main culprit of the war (FOCUS, 3 May 2022). Other surveys conducted by the Public Opinion Research Centre in the spring and autumn of 2022 showed that support for the government's actions had significantly fallen. In autumn of the same year, only slightly more than two-fifths of respondents (42%) supported the government's actions in support of Ukraine, and slightly more than half (52%) disapproved (CVVM, 9 December 2022). One of the possible explanations is the Russian false narrative being promoted very actively, accompanied by high inflation and dramatic energy price rises (i.e., falling living standards) caused by the Russian invasion.

Several initiatives aimed at spreading the Ukraine narrative and fighting the pro-Russian one. The first were those fighting back against fake news coming from Russia, which plagued the Czecho-Slovak media ecosystem, blending Russian propaganda and anti-EU rhetoric. According to various estimates, Czech language disinformation outlets reached about 10% of the population (Brokes, 2020). Dominantly it was the work of NGOs and academic work focusing on fighting fake news (Gregor and Mlejnková, 2021). Fiala's government promised to fight disinformation; however, critical voices were quickly raised in warning of censorship and a return to non-democratic practices, so the government became very cautious and lenient in this regard. Czech disinformation networks continued to spread their word and help the radicalization of society. The main narrative of the "alternative" websites has been repeating that Russia is the victim of Western aggression; it has the right to defend itself; Ukraine is a puppet of the West; corrupted country with no right for sovereignty; Ukrainians are fascists and terrorists (Kartous, 24 February 2022).

⁴ www.aeronet.cz, www.protiproud.cz, www.ceskobezcenzury.cz, www.prvnizpravy.cz, www.czechfreepress.cz, www.voxpopuliblog.cz, www.exanpro.cz, and www.skrytapravda.cz.

The Czech Republic faced an unforeseen and unprecedented influx of Ukrainian refugees. Around 500,000 people displaced by the war secured temporary protection visas in the country; by the end of 2022, about one-fifth of these refugees had returned home (Plevák, 2023). The Czech Republic initially handled this crisis with aplomb, as there was extraordinary support from the Czech state, society and NGOs. However, the Ukraine refugees were later seen by the less well-off and by pro-Russian groups as a burden on the Czech state, and a *us and them* divide was created. The crisis of substantial inflation and energy price hikes contributed to a rise in the number of disaffected citizens. The anti-Ukrainian narrative began to appear in politics, depicting Ukrainians as those who take jobs, social benefits and places in nursery schools and basic schools, at the expense of Czechs; followed by the narrative of withdrawal from sending financial, technical or military aid and rather invest in the Czech Republic in the name of peace.

Czech radicals started to mobilize; one of the biggest demonstrations was attended by around 70,000 people in Prague in September 2022. Pro-Russian activists followed up on anti-vaxxer events held earlier, keeping both the narrative and the target audience very much the same. Such mobilization exploited the poverty themes, including the energy price crisis and the pursuit of a peaceful solution to the war in Ukraine. The overall political opportunity structure in the Czech Republic in 2022 favored pro-Ukraine groups. The political elites, along with the media, expressed solidarity with Ukraine and this created an environment conducive for civil society to garner support for the pro-Ukraine agenda.

Themes and strategies: in the name of Ukraine, in the name of the Czech Republic, in the name of us all

Czechs donated nearly five billion crowns for humanitarian aid and more than one billion for weapons and defense equipment in the first two years after the invasion. In 2023, their willingness to contribute dropped significantly, and some organizations received a fraction of what they collected in the first months of the war (Smatana 2024). The already well-established People in Need Foundation was most successful. Though organizations which started from scratch, those that collect money for weapons, are thriving and can be regarded as the most successful projects.

Table 2. Fundraising by civil society organizations

Fundraising for	Organizations involved	Raised in 2022 (€)	Raised in 2023 (€)	Total 2022-2023 (€)
Humanitarian aid in Ukraine	People in Need	89,401,534	7,960,241	97,361,775
	Czech Red Cross	12,795,910	199,006	12,994,816
Aid for refugees in the Czech Republic	Caritas	6,516,661	398,012	6,914,673
	SIMI	18,667	5,095	23,765
Weapons and military equipment for Ukraine	WfU ⁵	19,900,604	6,724,852	26,625,465
	MoN	13,054,796	1,830,855	14,885,651

References: Smatana, 2024; Novák, 2023; SIMI, 2022.

The amount of coded Facebook (FB) data is in Table 3. There is significant drop in the activity in the case of humanitarian organizations which do not focus solely on Ukraine. Their focus moved to other issues, e.g., earthquakes in Turkey and Morocco, floods in Slovenia and the humanitarian

⁵ The project under the Ministry of Defence of the Czech Republic, Ukraine embassy in the Czech Republic, nuclear physicist Dana Drábová and Czech entrepreneur and philanthropist Dalibor Dědek.

situation in Gaza. The organizations set up with a unique goal – the acquisition of weapons and equipment for the Ukraine army – even increased their activity.

Table 3. Facebook posts by civil society organizations

Posts on	Organizations involved	Year 1	Year 2
Humanitarian aid in Ukraine	People in Need	396	149
	Czech Red Cross	65	13
Aid to refugees in the Czech Republic	Caritas	281	22
	SIMI	86	54
Weapons and other military equipment for Ukraine	Weapons for Ukraine ⁶	73	218
	Memory of Nations	97	112

Notes: Year 1: FB posts 24/02/2022 to 24/20/2023, Year 2: FB posts 24/02/2023 to 24/02/2024

Organizations with a focus on humanitarian aid in Ukraine. The Czech Red Cross (ČČK), a humanitarian organization operating throughout the Czech Republic, is a part of the International Red Cross. The organization works in the humanitarian, social, health and health-education fields. Their website (www.cervenyriz.eu) mentions the war only as part of information for Ukrainian refugees coming to the Czech Republic and it offers only infrequent reports on material support delivered to Ukraine. On their Facebook page, a primary communication tool, we observed a decline in activity since the Russian invasion. During the first month, ČČK posted contributions daily; most posts are from the first six months of the war. From September 2022 to February 2023 mentions of Ukraine declined dramatically (six posts out of 65). Only 13 posts were published during the second year of the war.

In general, ČČK's posts worked predominantly with only prognostic framing, outlining immediate measures taken to mitigate the impact of war on civilians (see Table 4). Where we identified diagnostic framing – in about one-third of posts – the impact of the war on children and civilians (endangered civilians) dominated. In the prognostic framing, the organization emphasized the need for financial help (calls for financial support), coordinated and fast assistance to Ukraine or Ukrainian refugees, and deliveries of medical supplies and vehicles (mostly ambulances). In the second year of the war, the prognostic framing narrowed down and simplified to a narrative of coordinated, long-term and professional assistance. Motivational framing was very rare (about 10% of posts). These few posts expressed gratitude in the first year of the war (Ukrainian people being grateful to the Czech people for help and support). We identified we-ness – i.e., building a shared identity of Czechs and Ukrainians as one. We also found that volunteers involved in the help were highlighted. An accent on coordinated and professional help, which is fast and targeted, served as subliminal reassurance that we could handle the situation. ČČK often published posts listing what had been successfully achieved (what was delivered, what kind of help was assured etc.). The communications were very practically focused, without any intense sentiment.

Člověk v tísni (People in Need) is a major Czech humanitarian NGO, active both domestically and internationally (in South and Central America, Asia, Africa and Europe) since 1992. It became one of the largest non-profit organizations in Central Europe. Its website (www.peopleinneed.net) serves as a communication platform alongside social media.

⁶ The project was developed by the Ministry of Defence of the Czech Republic, Ukraine embassy in the Czech Republic, nuclear physicist Dana Drábová and Czech entrepreneur and philanthropist Dalibor Dědek.

Table 4. ČČK and People in Need: framing and strategies

	ČČK	People in Need
Diagnostic framing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Impact on children – Impact on civilians – Psychological impact – Refugees – Humanitarian crisis – War crimes and breaking international humanitarian law – Endangerment of humanitarian workers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Impact on children – Impact on civilians – Psychological impact – Refugees – Humanitarian crisis – War crimes and breaking humanitarian international law – Integration of refugees – Disinformation – Destabilization of neighboring countries – Threat to the security of all Europe – Russian hybrid warfare against Europe (Russian information warfare; migration as a tool of Russian hybrid warfare) – Applying collective guilt to Russians and Belarusians – Ukrainian Roma people as refugees – Czech citizens in need
Prognostic framing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Fundraising – Coordinated and fast assistance – Delivery of medical supplies – Delivery of vehicles – Psychological assistance – Compliance with the Geneva Convention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Material aid – Coordinated support for Ukraine – Fundraising – Integration – Awareness campaigns – Psychological assistance – Volunteering
Motivational framing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Gratitude (Ukrainian people being grateful to the Czech people for help and support) – We-ness (“we are all in this together”) – Solidarity – Commitment of volunteers – Wellbeing and safety 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Humanity – Solidarity – Solidarity among Ukrainian people – Wellbeing and safety – We-ness – Unbreakable spirit of Ukrainian people – Moral imperative to protect human rights – Threat to global food security – Threat to democracy and freedom in Europe
Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Benefit concerts – Personal stories of Ukrainians – Thanks to donors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Personal stories of Ukrainians – Thanks to donors – Benefit concerts – Art performances – Reports from Ukraine – Real Gift project

The dedicated “SOS Ukraine” section provides updates on aid for Ukraine and Ukrainian refugees (internally displaced persons, refugees in neighboring countries, and those in the Czech

Republic). This help is described as humanitarian, psychological and financial assistance. As of February 2024, over two million people had been helped. SOS Ukraine also includes a donation link, a helpline for Ukrainian refugees, and direct links to other websites offering and requesting help. The SOS Ukraine section also features articles on the topic, with a total of 135 texts posted during the first year and 52 in the second, detailing types of aid and personal stories. On the anniversaries of the start of the war, People in Need released an online brochure summarizing the humanitarian aid provided to date (www.clovekvtisni.cz/co-delame/humanitarni-a-rozvojova-pomoc/ukrajina).

On its Facebook account (www.facebook.com/clovekvtisni), the organization published several Ukraine-related posts per day, then the intensity decreased on several post per week. Since summer 2023, the intensity has decreased again and the attention shifted to other topics such as aid in other countries, assistance to Czech citizens, or environmental issues. Diagnostic framing in the first war year centered on two key problems: displacement/refugees (both internally in Ukraine and refugees travelling to the Czech Republic and other countries) and the impact of the war on civilians (see Table 4). These two diagnostic frames represented one-third of all diagnostic frames in the analyzed data. Specifically, within the impact on the civilian population, a lot attention was paid to children. The third largest frame was the diagnosis of the war as a humanitarian crisis. By autumn 2022, integration of refugees, particularly of children in schools, became more prominent. Minority issues, but consistently present over time, were the psychological impact of war on individuals, the violation of international humanitarian law, war crimes committed by Russia in Ukraine and disinformation that appeared as a security risk in connection with the war. At the very beginning of the war, topics such as the destabilization of neighboring countries as a result of the conflict, the threat to the security of the whole of Europe by Russia, Russian information warfare and migration as a tool of Russian hybrid warfare briefly and insignificantly appeared within the diagnostic frame. However, People in Need warned against applying collective guilt to Russians and Belarusians.

Two short-term and specific diagnostic frames emerged in April 2022: unequal support for Roma Ukrainian refugees, who lacked proper accommodation; and reassurance that aid to Ukrainians was not at the expense of Czechs in need. The diversity of diagnostic frames disappeared in the second year of the war. The “impact of the war on civilians” dominated, with humanitarian crisis reappearing only after the Kakhovka Dam’s destruction in June 2023.

Prognostic framing focused on material aid for Ukraine and refugees in countries like Moldova, and the need for coordinated assistance at both national and EU levels. In the second year, the long-term character of assistance was stressed. Another way to help Ukraine is through fundraising. In addressing the issue of displacement, integration is necessary. In the first year, People in Need communicated integration in three dimensions: the need for a systematic, long-term and strategic approach from the government; housing solutions for refugees; and the integration of children into schools. People in Need supported these efforts through educational materials, teacher training, and tutoring. Integration framing lessened in the second year, replaced by broader awareness campaigns and mental health support. Rare references were made to Russian accountability (imposing tough sanctions and applying international law), mainly in the first year.

Motivational frames appeared in about one-third of the posts, grounded mostly in humanity (moral imperative) and solidarity. Strong motivators for assistance included solidarity among Ukrainians themselves and the desire for a better and safer life for refugees. There was a minority mention of the symbol of the unbroken spirit of the Ukrainian nation, the moral imperative to protect human rights and reminders that Russian aggression threatened democracy and freedom throughout Europe and that the war in Ukraine, an important grain exporter, endangered global food security. A

shared identity of “we-ness” was cultivated in two ways. First, between Czechs and People in Need (slogan “We help people in Ukraine. Help us help”). Second, between Czechs and Ukrainians (“We are with them”, “We will win together”, “We are all Ukraine”, and the hashtag StandWithUkraine). Shared history was occasionally invoked through the historical events of 1968 Warsaw Pact invasion to Czechoslovakia. The motivational frame often relied on mobilization through compassion and fear. Compassion and fear were simultaneously associated with the personal stories of Ukrainians experiencing the horrors of war. Similar to the Czech Red Cross, People in Need builds its credible position by promoting an image of an effective and professional organization (slogans such as “Help with us! We can do it, we have been helping in Ukraine since 2014”) and through frequently published reports of achievements and donor acknowledgements.

Organizations with a focus on aid to refugees in the Czech Republic. Charita (Caritas) is the oldest charitable organization with a nationwide structure of archdiocesan and diocesan charities and the largest non-state provider of social and health services in the Czech Republic. Its first aim is to meet the basic living needs of a group of refugees who are particularly vulnerable due to their living situation – mothers with children, unaccompanied children, the elderly, people with specific needs caused by medical or psychological disabilities and people coming from war zones without basic equipment and personal connections in the Czech Republic.

We found the Caritas website (www.charita.cz) provided only a description of the project and a list of donors. Fundraising is supported by the stories of both volunteers and refugees who had found a new life in Czechia; the site avoided any framing by the organization itself (see Table 5). The first post on Facebook condemned the Russian aggression; other posts did not really tackle the issue and rather focused on the impact of war on civilians and the need to provide them with humanitarian aid. In the first half of 2022 the posts concentrated mainly on humanitarian aid; in the second half the themes were safety and helping refugees live happy lives. Caritas posted interviews with refugees (with a special focus on women), interviews with volunteers helping the refugees, videos from the war and information on how the organization has helped so far. Most prominent were the personal stories of female refugees who found a happy life in the Czech Republic and helped incoming refugees find the same. Motivational framing was not very prominent. In the second half of 2022, the call was for persisting in support no matter how long the war would take. In 2023, the number of FB posts dedicated to aid to Ukraine significantly dropped – only 46 out of the 493 posts were dedicated to aid in Ukraine, most of them posted during the first anniversary of Russia’s invasion of Ukraine and some after the blowing up of the Kakhovka Dam in June 2023 and the subsequent floods, in response to which Caritas sent drinking water to people affected. Besides that, the charity focused on aid to homeless people and seniors, helping after earthquakes in Syria, Turkey and Morocco, floods in Libya and Slovenia or the humanitarian crisis in Gaza.

SIMI (Association for integration and migration – www.migrace.com) gives assistance to refugees, helps in solving their basic needs and subsequent settlement, and provides interpretation, escorts, psychotherapeutic care, help in finding a job and financial support; aid for Ukrainian refugees is only one of the SIMI projects. The SIMI posts on Facebook mainly provide information for refugees about legal help, workshops, volunteers and housing and give background about the work of the organization. In our examination of the site, we found that, when mentioning the Russian invasion, it was done only in passing as part of information about how many refugees the organization had taken care of since the war began. The posts were informative in character and did not seem to serve a fundraising purpose. Neither did we find any change in the form or type of post over time; they remained informative throughout the whole two years.

Table 5. Caritas and SIMI: framing and strategies

	Caritas	SIMI
Diagnostic framing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – War in Ukraine – Refugees – Russian invasion – Russian aggression – Impact on civilians – Impact on children – Orphans – Poverty – Humanitarian catastrophe – War trauma 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Refugees – Russian invasion
Prognostic framing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Safety – Humanitarian aid – Integration – Prayer and worship – Housing, shelters – Material aid – Psychological aid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Integration – Housing, shelter – Psychological help – Legal counselling – Schooling
Motivational framing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Solidarity – Persist in support – Make people happy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – ---
Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Interviews with refugees – Interviews with volunteers – Videos from war – We make people happy – Orphans' stories – Boxing Day – Traditional door-to-door fundraising – Advent fundraising concerts – Rally 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – FB informative – Workshops – Lectures – Conferences – Multicultural events

Organizations with a focus on acquiring weapons and other military equipment for Ukraine. Numerous projects within the Czech Republic actively raise and allocate funds as well as equipment to support the needs of the Ukrainian armed forces. The project “Zbraně pro Ukrajinu” (Weapons for Ukraine), colloquially known by its more provocative name, “Dárek pro Putina” (Gift for Putin) emerged as an ad-hoc movement aiming to amass funds and supply armaments to the Ukrainian military. The project “Help Ukraine with the Memory of Nations” (or simply “Memory of Nations” – www.memoryofnations.eu/en/memory-ukraine), was launched by the non-profit entity, Post Bellum (<https://www.darujme.cz/projekt/1205934#aktuality>), which has conducted a myriad of initiatives since 2001. The two projects have distinct operational methodologies, engage with the public differently and employ unique fundraising strategies. The funds of Weapons for Ukraine are used mainly for weaponry, while Memory of Nations primarily invests in non-lethal military equipment.

The distinction is evident in the narratives they employ and their evolution since the onset of the Ukrainian conflict (see Table 6). Weapons for Ukraine primarily uses two fundraising avenues: first, through the commercial sale of thematic products and memorabilia via online stores (T-shirts, stickers and magnets expressing solidarity with Ukraine and dehumanizing Russia and Vladimir Putin);⁷ and second, by dedicating collections to specific armaments and ammunition, such as Czech-manufactured drones or upgraded T-72 tanks.⁸ In contrast, Memory of Nations engages in an ongoing fundraising campaign without allotting donations to specific items. However, it periodically discloses the resources it has acquired, such as medical supplies, bulletproof vests and drones, detailing their intended recipients.⁹

Both initiatives maintain a digital presence via websites and social media, aiming to mobilize public support. Each employs a distinctive narrative framed across three dimensions - diagnostic, prognostic, and motivational. These frames reveal both shared and unique features, evident in the analysis of their websites and Facebook pages. Differences stem from the platforms' nature and tailored content strategies: websites are relatively static, while Facebook allows more dynamic, emotionally engaging messaging attuned to Czech public sentiment.

Table 6. Weapons for Ukraine: framing and strategies.

	Weapons for Ukraine	Memory of Nations
Diagnostic framing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Defense of Ukraine – Defense of all of us – Russian aggression – Wars are won with weapons 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Ukraine bleeds – Saving human lives – Fight for freedom – Non-lethal support of the defenders
Prognostic framing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Fundraising – Expel Russian soldiers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Defense of free Ukraine – More lives to be saved
Motivational framing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – With your gifts, Ukrainians destroy the Russian invader – Buying weapons helps – We-ness (safety of Ukrainians and safety of all of us) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Solidarity – We-ness: no repetition of 1968 – A moral imperative to support human rights and democracy
Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Satirizing the Russians and Vladimir Putin – Interviews with soldiers – Interviews with volunteers – Videos from war – Photos of weapons delivered to the Ukrainian battlefield 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Interviews with soldiers – Personal stories showing the value of support – News from Ukrainian battlefield and background

The Weapons for Ukraine website mainly serves as an archive of fundraising activities, merchandise sales, project background, and social media links. While sufficient for basic framing analysis, it lacks narrative evolution. In contrast, Facebook functions as WfU's primary mobilization

⁷ See <https://www.zbraneproukrajinu.cz/e-shop/tricko-fuck-you-putin>

⁸ See <https://www.weaponstoukraine.com/kampane/cesky-tank-tomas-pro-ukrajinskou-armadu>

⁹ See <https://www.darujme.cz/projekt/1205934#aktuality>

tool. MoN offers a more detailed website, including donation options, Ukrainian news, and appeals. Its Facebook content reflects broader activities, especially around Czechoslovakia's communist past, but frequently ties back to Ukraine.

Analyzing diagnostic framing, both projects employed a limited set of fundamental codes. For WfU, the salient ones encompassed "defense of Ukraine", "defense of all of us" (in broader term of European and Western values), and "Russian aggression". Here, Ukraine was cast in a defensive role against an aggressor. This struggle transcended mere territorial defense. As articulated by the project, "by defending their country, Ukrainians are defending all of us and fighting for our shared values." Its digital narrative amplified this sentiment, asserting, "we are here for those who can see that Ukrainians are championing our collective cause and that it remains our obligation to assist them." Notably, WfU eschews terms such as "war in Ukraine" and "Ukrainian-Russian war", favoring more assertive "Russian aggression".¹⁰ The initiative openly demarcated itself from humanitarian campaigns using slogan "wars are won with weapons".

In contrast, MoN emphasized non-lethal aid, humanitarian urgency, and themes like "Ukraine bleeds" and "saving lives". While WfU engaged directly with the Russian narrative, MoN tactfully navigated around generalizing about Russians or Russia. Instead, it highlighted Ukrainian defenders and a broader humanitarian tragedy.

In the prognostic framing the overarching goal of the two initiatives converged on "soliciting funds to bolster Ukraine's defense against Russian aggression". As the conflict evolved, WfU emphasis shifted from a mere defensive stance to one of counter-offensive by 2023, integrating merchandise sales into its mobilization. T-shirts like "Fuck You, Putin" became symbolic, blending pro-Ukraine messaging with Czech public sentiment. It has transcended its initial scope, morphing into an emblematic slogan, gaining widespread traction.¹¹

In contrast, MoN was found to adopt a more nuanced approach. Rather than direct confrontation with Russian forces within Ukraine, its focus was directed to supplying Ukraine with non-lethal military equipment, particularly catering to "frontline combatants and elite military units", invoking historical parallels with communist era in Czechoslovakia. Its framing centers on preserving life and defending democratic values, aligning with its broader mission: "We refuse to be passive observers to the brutalities and aggression our allies endure, simply because they resonate with our shared ideals of freedom and democracy."

¹⁰ It's intriguing to note the deliberate manipulation of language in the project's basic information. The term used to describe "Russian" in Czech is traditionally "ruský", spelled with a single "S". However, the project has deliberately altered this to "russký", doubling the "S". This nuanced change is not mere oversight but an intentional move to draw parallels between Nazi Germany and its notorious SS troops and the present-day Russian regime and its military forces. Such linguistic adjustments, while subtle, play a powerful role in influencing perceptions and are prevalent in communications among Czech pro-Ukrainian and anti-Russian online communities.

¹¹ A pivotal factor that has augmented the reach and prominence of the initiative is the dissemination of photographs featuring prominent Czech personalities donning the T-shirt described. Their act of sharing these images on digital social platforms not only endorsed but also heightened the visibility of the WfU project. This widespread acclaim and recognition subsequently culminated in the establishment of a dedicated website, termed 'Fuck You Putin Club' (<https://www.fuckyouputin.club/>). Within this digital platform, visitors can access a curated gallery that showcases renowned figures, including Czech journalists, the Czech minister of defence and other distinguished individuals, all of whom are depicted wearing the T-shirt in question.

Motivational framing of both initiatives is embedded within the diagnostic framing, accentuating the defense of Ukraine, advocating for the expulsion of Russian aggressors and underscoring the imperative to support those who stand in defense not only of Ukraine but of broader shared values; constructing us vs. them identity: defenders of freedom vs. Russian aggressors. Each purchase or contribution can potentially mitigate the conflict's casualty toll and it is framed as humanitarian act, countering claims that such aid prolongs the war. Notably absent from WfU's narrative were broader geopolitical or human rights discourses.

Meanwhile, MoN taps into Czech historical memory, especially the 1968 invasion, to build emotional resonance. During key anniversaries, it explicitly links past Soviet aggression to Russian current actions.

The strategies employed by the two initiatives were markedly distinct in their approach and focus. WfU frequently employed mockery directed at the Russians and Vladimir Putin. It didn't shy away from showcasing the harsh realities of the war. MoN adopted a more solemn tone, concentrating on lives saving. Despite these differences, both projects employed the personal narratives of Ukrainian soldiers to appeal to potential donors and show impact.

Since the spring of 2023, their narratives have increasingly acknowledged each other, underlining the complementary value of lethal and non-lethal support. While MoN kept a steady pace of posts, WfU markedly increased its social media activity over time.

Discussion

The social movement mobilization in the Czech Republic in response to the Russian invasion to Ukraine provides a rich case for analyzing the intersection of civil society activism, political opportunity structures, and strategic framing under conditions of prolonged crisis. The study has revealed both the initiate success and subsequent attenuation of pro-Ukrainian mobilization.

The most striking finding of the research is the divergence in the use of diagnostic, prognostic, and motivational framing between different types of organizations. Humanitarian NGOs, including People in Need, Czech Red Cross, Caritas and SIMI, largely eschewed overtly political or moral framing in favor of a technocratic and emotionally restrained narrative. Their communications were dominated by pragmatic descriptions of material aid delivery, expressions of gratitude, and individual-level human interest stories. Even where diagnostic framing was present, it was typically limited to describing the suffering of civilians or the challenges of refugee integration, with only limited reference to the structural causes of the war. Similarly, motivational framing was sparse, relying on assumed moral consensus and compassion, rather than on sustained rhetorical effort to justify or reinforce mobilization.

This relative restraint can be interpreted through the lens of both organizational identity and political opportunity structures. Humanitarian NGOs often seek to preserve neutrality and avoid explicit political engagement. Such an approach can help maintain donor trust, preserve access in volatile contexts, and avoid polarization. In the Czech context, this restraint was initially reinforced by a strong pro-Ukrainian consensus among political elites, the media, and the public. In the early months of the war, support for Ukraine was widespread and uncontroversial. The need to engage in persuasive motivational framing was therefore perceived as unnecessary.

However, our findings suggest that this strategy may have had diminishing returns over time. As public attention shifted, inflation soared, and counter-narratives (including pro-Russian disinformation) gained ground, the initial moral clarity of the war began to fade in the public imagination. Under these changing circumstances, the failure to recalibrate framing strategies may

have contributed to declining engagement. Despite continuing their activities on the ground, most humanitarian organizations saw a sharp decline in both fundraising and visibility related to Ukraine by the second year of the war. The absence of a dynamic or evolving narrative may have reduced their ability to maintain attention in a saturated media environment.

In contrast, initiatives focused on military aid to Ukraine—such as Weapons for Ukraine and Memory of Nations—adopted much more assertive framing strategies. These organizations employed clear and emotionally resonant diagnostic frames, identifying Russia as an aggressor, framing the war as a threat to broader European values, and presenting Ukraine as the frontline of a larger geopolitical struggle. Their prognostic frames were action-oriented and direct: donate to buy weapons, support the Ukrainian military, and stop the advance of authoritarianism. Motivational framing was central to their strategy, employing powerful appeals to collective identity, moral urgency, and historical memory. This was particularly evident in the deployment of 1968 as a symbolic parallel, linking contemporary Russian aggression to past Soviet repression and thereby tapping into a widely shared and affectively charged historical schema.

The strategic use of humor, satire, and consumer culture—evident in the WfU campaign's merchandising and provocative slogans—also played a role in sustaining engagement. While potentially controversial, this approach proved effective in targeting segments of the Czech population that might be historically skeptical of solemn moral appeals but responsive to irony and irreverence. In this sense, WfU's communication strategy aligns with broader insights from political psychology and cultural sociology: emotional engagement, narrative clarity, and symbolic resonance matter deeply in sustaining social mobilization, particularly in the context of distant or protracted conflicts (Snow & Benford, 1988; Rogers et al., 2018).

Memory of Nations offers a hybrid case. While supporting military efforts, it refrained from lethal framing and instead focused on supplying protective and medical equipment. It appealed to values of dignity, liberty, and historical justice—again using the memory of communist-era repression as a narrative bridge to contemporary Ukraine. Importantly, MoN framed its efforts as aligned with humanitarian principles while simultaneously invoking political values. This dual framing allowed it to maintain moral legitimacy while mobilizing significant resources.

These contrasting approaches allow us to draw several analytical conclusions. First, the effectiveness of mobilization appears to be closely tied to the strategic alignment of frames with both the organizational identity and the political context. Second, the data reveal that framing is not a one-time act but a continuous process. As Caiani (2023) rightly notes, the temporality of framing is crucial. Frames must be periodically refreshed, adapted, and recalibrated to remain resonant. Third, the Czech case illustrates the importance of collective memory and national identity in shaping mobilization. The use of historical analogies was not merely rhetorical flourish. It functioned as a powerful mobilizing frame that connected the present conflict to an emotionally encoded past. This demonstrates how cultural resources can be activated to reinforce solidarity, define moral boundaries, and counter apathy.

Concluding remarks

The Czech case of pro-Ukrainian social mobilization demonstrates the importance of framing strategies, organizational identity, and political opportunity structures in shaping civil society responses to international crises. Over time, declining public engagement revealed the limitations of static or apolitical communication, especially in a shifting political landscape marked by disinformation and economic stress.

Looking ahead, civil society actors in the Czech Republic will need to navigate a more fragmented and polarized public sphere. If they wish to sustain engagement and solidarity with Ukraine in the face of prolonged conflict fatigue, they must adapt their framing strategies to reenergize public attention and trust. This may involve blending humanitarian messaging with values-based appeals, drawing on culturally resonant narratives, and leveraging new forms of digital storytelling. Moreover, the case highlights a broader challenge for European civil societies: to balance moral clarity with inclusivity, and to maintain momentum in support of democratic values, even as domestic pressures mount and geopolitical uncertainties persist.

Funding

This text was written at Masaryk University with the support of a Specific University Research Grant provided by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic.

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